

**Assessment of Innovative Instructional Strategies on Teaching and Learning of
Electrical/Electronic Technology Concepts among Federal University Students in South-
South, Nigeria**

OGBEBOR, Samuel Osamede¹

ogbebor@aauekpoma.edu.ng

08078180039

OVIawe, Jane Itohan¹

janeoviaw@aauekpoma.edu.ng

08055601983

¹Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Ambrose Alli University, Edo State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study examined innovative instructional strategies on teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology concept among Federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions. The descriptive survey research design was adopted with a population of 128 electrical/electronic technology students of year three and four from four federal universities in the during 2023/2024 academic session. No sample technique was used because of its manageable size. The instruments “Improving Teaching and Learning of Electrical/Electronic Technology for Sustainable Development through Innovative Approaches (ITLEETSDIA) for data collection was the structured questionnaire that was further subjected to face validity by three research experts. A reliability coefficient value of 0.79 was obtained using the Cronbach Alpha statistical tool. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings showed that blended learning as an innovative approach greatly improves the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities. Furthermore, electronic learning was found to greatly enhance the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development. Based on these findings, it was recommended that an Innovative approach be made by electrical/ electronic lecturers to improve the student’s practical skills through the use of collaborative learning for sustainable development among others.

Keywords: *Electrical/electronic technology, sustainable development, teaching and learning, blended learning, electronic learning.*

Introduction

Sustainability refers to how humans should use the environment while protecting it for coming generations (Ayres, 2008). According to Todaro and Smith (2011), development is a process that raises living standards, self-esteem, and freedom to improve human lives. Sustainable development, then, satisfies current demands without jeopardizing the capacity of future generations to meet their own, according to the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987). Sen (1999) said that a person living in extreme poverty and lacking any education or skills cannot contribute to the growth of a country. Edokpolor and Owenbiugie (2017) cited the World Commission on Environment and Development, which defines

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15669518>

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sustainable development as the process of addressing current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to fulfill their own. Sustainable development is a growth approach that aims to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It encompasses three interconnected dimensions: environmental integrity, economic viability, and social equity (Coulibaly, 2019). This approach is characterized by its ongoing, goal-oriented, long-term, and collaborative nature, and it has an impact on many facets of life.

In Nigeria, sustainable development can be defined as a growth model that gives the current generation a respectable standard of living, dignity, and freedom while guaranteeing that future generations have access to necessities like food, shelter, healthcare, clothing, and security (UNDP, 2020). Furthermore, Ogbebor and Osagiede (2024) characterize sustainable development as a progressive strategy aimed at meeting present needs and opportunities while preserving the environmental elements that support these needs, thus enabling the resolution of future challenges. The goal of education is to instill in students the necessary values, abilities, and attitudes to enable them to contribute productively to a changing society. Teaching and learning are the methods used in educational institutions to help students acquire these qualities. Without a teaching-learning process, it is evident that no educational institution can effectively convey knowledge to students. Because of this, instruction and learning are among the most crucial components of educational establishments, among which technical vocational education and training (TVET) is one.

TVET is a broad term that encompasses all elements of the educational process, including general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the development of knowledge, attitudes, and practical skills relevant to a variety of occupations in the social and economic spheres. In its education policy paper, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) described TVET as including those parts of the educational process that include the study of technologies and allied sciences in addition to general education. This includes learning about jobs in different areas of social and economic life as well as practical skills, attitudes, and knowledge. UNESCO (2024) defines TVET as a type of education created especially to satisfy industry and worker demands. Therefore, TVET is regarded as a crucial tool for preparing the workforce for new job markets, which are frequently referred to as the "jobs of tomorrow" (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2023). According to recent research (UNESCO, 2024; World Bank, 2023b), efficient TVET systems are essential for promoting sustainable economic growth as well as individual empowerment, especially in low- and middle-income nations. As a crucial component of general education, TVET serves several functions, including preparing students for occupations so they can contribute successfully to the workforce, encouraging lifelong learning, cultivating responsible citizenship, assisting in environmentally sustainable development, and reducing poverty through pre-technical and vocational education (World Bank, 2023a).

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TVET is a program that is offered at different institutions to learn scientific knowledge and practical skills for a country's technical and economic growth. It covers education, training, and skill development in a range of professions, manufacturing procedures, services, and means of subsistence. Technical, industrial, industrial arts, technology, or industrial technical education are some of the programs offered by TVET. These can be used interchangeably as the same field of study because they are related. A variety of specializations make up industrial technical education. The development of skills is emphasized in every facet of industrial technical education. Its areas of expertise include electronics and electrical technologies.

TVET's electrical and electronics technology specialization is one of the skills-oriented programs that students need to learn through instruction (Bassauldo & Toby, 2004). TVET's electrical and electronics program covers certain topics related to electrical and electronic technologies. These contents include, but are not limited to, integrated circuits, microprocessors, transistors, amplifiers, and electronic instruments; digital logic circuits; electrical installation; electrical devices and machines; electronic communication; semiconductor devices and circuits; and electrical and electronics drafting. Various tasks involving a wide range of skills are included in these content categories, and they can be taught and learned in a typical classroom, laboratory/workshop, or with the use of suitable technologies.

It is important to view teaching as a multifaceted activity. Many people consider it to be a classroom activity (Offorma, 2002), but teaching is more than that in this present era and in all its honesty. Thus, teaching is the process of imparting relevant, useful, and appropriate skills to students in any format, location, and/or time so they may effectively fulfill the demands of a changing society. Making desired behavioral changes in students is the main goal of instruction (Ogwo & Oranu, 2006). Learning is the phrase for this desired change. According to Farrant in Aleburu and Olunsanya (2007), learning is the process by which we pick up and hold onto traits, abilities, information, and attitudes that are not related to our innate behavioral patterns of physical development. Accordingly, learning is the process by which a person's behavior changes as a result of gaining relevant and useful abilities that allow them to explore and thrive in their community. The student can demonstrate these linked talents when faced with electrical and electronic tasks or obstacles thanks to the skills they have learned in electrical and electronic programs. Traditional classroom settings are not the only way to teach and learn skills or content in TVET's electrical and electronic technology program. Insufficient human and material resources are available in Nigeria for students enrolled in TVET programs in electrical and electronic technology to acquire the necessary skills. For this reason, other means such as ICTs are very necessary because they help learners irrespective of location and time. In addition, many electrical and electronic devices, tools, equipment, and appliances are not produced in Nigeria, hence the need to support learners with innovative approaches without waiting until there are sufficient human and material resources to facilitate the teaching of the program.

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Despite these admirable goals, electrical and electronic technology are taught and learned in public universities using traditional methods that are characterized by teacher-centeredness (Gibbs & Coffey, 2004). Under these methods, teachers are always viewed as experts playing important roles, while students are merely passive listeners. This method is also found to be unsuitable, particularly in the 21st century, where information is obtained through the use of media, and training young people for sustainable development necessitates a shift from traditional teaching to innovativeness (EI-Khawas & Salmi, 2001). Innovative approaches are strategies or methods that are applied by facilitators to simulate learning while encouraging learners to rediscover them through their capabilities, skills, acquisition, and optimal attainment of learning outcomes (Scott, Yield, & Hendry, 2007). The adoption of innovative approaches in teaching and learning electrical/electronic technology aims to provide effective and efficient practices for real-life electrical/electronic problems.

Innovativeness connotes improvement, development, and renewable associated with the teaching and learning process. All areas of learning and disciplines are affected by this innovativeness. In university education, innovation offers students the chance to come up with ideas by using various methods, such as work-based learning, online teaching, student-centered and self-directed learning, collaborative learning, teleconferencing, blended learning, and electronic learning. These approaches, among other things, encourage students to be active learners who work in groups and effectively relate to others and their surroundings (Yu & Hang, 2010). Additionally, these approaches offer more opportunities for interaction and collaboration between students and between students and teachers (Parajuli, 2016). Given the variety of approaches found in innovation, the current study aims to examine blended and electronic learning approaches, which were chosen because they integrate different styles using different media.

As a novel technique, blended learning is a hybrid that delivers individualized, differentiated training to a group of students by fusing the advantages of online learning with traditional schooling (Powell, Walson, Staley, Patrick, Horn, Fetzer, & Verma 2015). Direct and indirect education, group learning, computer-assisted learning, and individual training are all incorporated into this learning process. The use of this type of learning, known as b-learning, in electrical and electronic technology at public universities is thought to allow students to freely engage in the teaching and learning process. Osguthorpe and Graham (2013) support this idea by stating that b-learning has aided students in preparing for classes, reviewing materials, researching the subject, and conducting their own self-evaluation. Similar research also demonstrated that b-learning has a favorable impact on students' positive perceptions (Ates, Urali & Guneyce, 2008) and lesson attitudes (EL-Deghaidy & Nouby, 2018). These scientific findings unequivocally show how effective blended learning is at fostering students' learning and knowledge. Following the continued usage of face-to-face interaction, which is primarily traditional, there is still debate on whether electrical and electronic technology has been included for the purpose of promoting sustainable growth in South-South public universities.

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Electronic learning is another strategy to enhance electrical and electronic technology instruction.

Electronic learning is sometimes referred to as e-learning. This relates to the distribution of educational resources via electronic media. It entails using digital technology to its fullest capacity in order to introduce a concept, view it in several contexts, make connections with prior knowledge, and facilitate discussions that improve students' comprehension of the topic and its context (Asogwa, 2011). E-learning involves a situation in which the instructor handles a convergence of digital material from a wide range of sources and devices presenting, discussing, and reflecting on a subject with a class group. This suggests that it is a collection of human tools aimed at a certain group to help them absorb information. Thus, one could say that it represents an approach that offers access to education and training to learners while emancipating them from the limits of time and space thanks to its flexibility. Adelalu and Adu (2015) showed that it boosts the possibility of employing carefully planned computer programs to ensure that learners are accurately and systematically trained. This further clarifies how e-learning might enhance electrical and electronic technology instruction in public universities. Supporting the applicability of this strategy, Osadebe et al. (2017) showed that university students' academic performance has greatly increased thanks to online libraries.

The current study attempts to provide empirical evidence to further authenticate the relevance of e-learning to electrical/electronic technology. Although the study provided empirical evidence on the relevance of online libraries, which is an aspect of e-learning, no mention was made of a given discipline and perhaps how it has promoted the acquisition of relevant skills and competencies for the promotion of sustainable development. This is concerning because, in the twenty-first century, academic institutions in South-South Nigeria's public universities must use technology to teach and learn a variety of subjects, including electrical and electronic technology, in order to promote sustainable development.

Statement of the problem

In Nigeria, TVET programs involving electrical and electronic technology have struggled with a lack of enough and possibly insufficiently skilled human resources to teach the students the necessary skills (Oviawe, & Uwamieye, 2018). Due to the school system's emphasis on the traditional classroom setting, the extent of skill acquisition in electrical and electronic technology programs has also been limited by the lack of workshop space, tools, and other material resources (Owo & Deebom, 2020). This study therefore critically x-rayed innovative instructional strategies on teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology concept among Federal universities in South-South Nigeria required for the promotion of sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

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The objective of the study was to determine the extent to which innovative approaches can aid in improving the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Ascertain the extent to which blended learning can improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the extent to which electronic learning can improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study:

- i. To what extent can blended learning improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent can electronic learning improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Methodology

The study followed the descriptive survey research design. This design, according to Nworgu (2015) focuses on researching a group of people or products by collecting and analyzing data from only a few deemed representations of the full group. The survey included 135 students from four federal institutions that provide the program, 78 of them were in their third year, and 57 of them were in their final year of vocational and technical education. The department's records and exams from the 2023–2024 academic year at several institutions served as the information source. Using a census population eliminated the requirement for sample techniques due to the population's manageable size. The instrument for data collection was the structured questionnaire adapted from Asuquo, Olori, and Adizu (2022) titled, Improving Teaching and Learning of Electrical/Electronic Technology for Sustainable Development through Innovative Approaches (ITLEETSDIA). The questionnaire was made up of two sections. Section A provided demographic information of the respondents, while section B had two clusters providing information on the research questions and structured on a four-point rating scale of very great extent (4-points), great extent (3-points), moderate extent (2-points), and low extent (1-point). The questionnaire was further subjected to face validity by three research experts, two from the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Ambrose Alli University, and one from the Measurement and Evaluation Department, University of Benin, both in Edo State, Nigeria. The reliability coefficient value of 0.79 was obtained using the

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Cronbach Alpha statistical tool. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Decision-making was based on a criterion mean of 2.50. Mean scores of 2.50 and above were regarded to a great extent, while below 2.50 was low.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: To what extent can blended learning improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on the extent to which blended learning can improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development (n = 128)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	S D	Remark
1.	Enable me to evaluate my knowledge of electrical/electronic technology.	2.91	0.75	Great extent
2.	Influences my attitude towards electrical/electronic tasks.	2.81	0.82	Great extent
3.	Preparing me to solve electrical/electronic faults.	2.61	0.87	Great extent
4.	Improve fast comprehension of electrical/electronic tasks.	2.84	0.91	Great extent
5.	Improve fast comprehension of electrical/electronic tasks.	2.69	0.89	Great extent
6.	Improve my practical skills in electrical/electronic technology	2.71	0.85	Great extent
7.	Encouraging diversity in learning to be abreast with fault tracing in electrical/electronic components.	2.87	0.70	Great extent
8.	Improve my knowledge of how to rectify electrical/electronic faults	2.91	0.89	Great extent
9.	Improve my knowledge of the identification of tools and instruments used in electrical/electronic technology	2.67	0.84	Great extent
10.	Improve my knowledge of the use of tools and instruments used in electrical/electronic technology	2.93	0.86	Great extent
	Cluster mean	2.84		Great extent

Table 1 had the mean scores of great extent for all the items and standard deviation ranging from 0.70 to 0.91. The cluster mean of 2.84 further indicated that the extent to which blended learning can improve teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development was to a great extent in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: Determine the extent to which electronic learning can improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South, Nigeria.

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Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on the extent to which electronic learning can improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development (n = 128)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	S D	Remark
1.	Building problem-solving skills for active participation in electrical /electronic technology	2.79	0.72	Great extent
2.	Improve my attitude towards learning electrical/electronic technology	2.76	0.69	Great extent
3.	Improve practical learning in electrical/electronic technology	2.44	0.85	low extent
4.	Aid in involvement in real-life situations in electrical/electronic technology	2.71	0.67	Great extent
5.	Encouraging the curiosity to learn to achieve financial independence through electrical/electronic technology	2.79	0.81	Great extent
6.	Improving self-development for economic opportunities and diversification in electrical/electronic technology	2.67	0.89	Great extent
7.	Improving knowledge by engaging in practical exercises in fault tracing in electrical/electronic technology	2.81	0.79	Great extent
8.	Improving knowledge on the use of tools and instrument use in electrical/electronic technology	2.94	0.68	Great extent
9.	Improving knowledge of fault identification and rectification in electrical/electronic technology	2.65	0.74	Great extent
10.	Improving knowledge of the use of innovative technology in electrical/electronic technology	2.87	0.83	Great extent
	Cluster mean	2.71		Great extent

Table 2 shows that respondents had mean scores of great extents for nine items, except item three with mean scores of low extents. The standard deviation ranged from 0.67 to 0.89, indicating the closeness of the mean scores. The cluster mean of 2.71 further revealed that to a great extent, electronic learning can improve teaching and learning of electrical/electrical technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South Nigeria.

Discussion of Finding

The study shows that blended learning as an innovative approach can greatly improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South Nigeria. The recognition of these enormous contributions may not have been unconnected with the fact that blended learning incorporates various strategies in teaching and learning to make it cooperative. This learning is acknowledged by respondents to touch various aspects of human capabilities in such areas as aid to evaluate knowledge of electrical/electronic technology, influences attitude towards electrical/electronic tasks, preparation towards solving electrical/electronic faults, improve fast comprehension of electrical/electronic task, improve practical skills in electrical/electronic technology, encouraging diversity in learning to be abreast with faults tracing in electrical/electronic

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components, improved knowledge on how to rectify electrical/electronic faults, improved knowledge on the identification of tools and instrument used in electrical/electronic technology, improved knowledge on the use of tools and instruments used in electrical/electronic technology, the finding also corroborates with Osguthorpeve and Graham (2013) study that students were equipped with the knowledge and skills to conduct self-evaluation themselves. By having this appraisal, it is believed that lapses or weaknesses identified will be adequately addressed to offer proper adaptability in various facets of electrical/electronic technology toward achieving sustainable development. This view also agrees with the findings of exhibiting positive attitudes by Deghaidy and Nouby (2018). The show of positive attitudes by students is believed to help in inspiring them to explore and identify opportunities capable of reducing the shortage of skilled manpower incapable of solving lingering unemployed situations in society.

The study shows that electronic learning can greatly improve the teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology for sustainable development in public universities in South-South Nigeria. The recognition of this extent is premised on the fact that meeting technological challenges in the technological era of the 21st century calls for the aggressive application of technology in teaching-learning situations. This is also true considering that electronic learning involves the integration of various media interventions for the facilitation of the teaching-learning process. Supporting its relevance in learning situations, it was found to have significantly improved the academic progress of students in the university according to Osadebe, et al (2017). No wonder, electronic learning was reported as having the potentials of digital technology in Building problem solving skills for active participation in electrical/electronic technology, stimulate my interest in learning to be self-reliant in electrical/electronic technology, Improving practical learning to be self-dependent in electrical/electronic technology, involvement in real life events to be enterprising in electrical/electronic technology, encouraging he curiosity to learn to achieving financial independent, Improving self-development for economic opportunities and diversification, improving knowledge by engaging in practical exercise in fault tracing in electrical/electronic technology, improving knowledge on the use of tools and instrument use in electrical/electronic technology, improving knowledge on fault identification and rectification in electrical/electronic technology, improving knowledge on the use of innovative technology in in electrical/electronic technology, thus enhances students understanding of the concept and context (Asogwa, 2011, Asuquo, Olori & Adizu, 2022). It then presupposes that with adequate application of this learning, students will be provided with adequate knowledge and skills capable of promoting sustainable development. This promotes self-reliance among prospective graduates in electrical/electronic technology.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the application of innovative approaches to teaching and learning in electrical/electronic technology was found to greatly promote sustainable development in public

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universities in South-South Nigeria. This objective was achieved in this study through the use of blended and electronic learning which components of innovative approaches are.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

- i. Innovative approaches be made by electrical/ electronic lecturers to improve the student's practical skills through the use of collaborative learning for sustainable development.
- ii. Effort should be made by electrical/ electronic lecturers to optimize the use of experiential learning styles on students for the promotion of sustainable development.

Acknowledgements:

The authors of this study wish to express their profound appreciation to all the students who took the time to participate in the study. The authors also wish to express their immense gratitude to all the research assistants who took time to administer the research instruments directly on the participants.

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